

ISic0845

I.Sicily inscription 0845

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

From the catacombs (unspecified), Siracusa

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις) .

2. ἐντάδε κεῖταιε

3. ΕὐνώηΕὐνόη δούλην

4. ΚωρηνίδοςΚοριννίδος

Apparatus

Text after IG

Kaibel suggests correcting to Κορηλίας

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492473

EDCS 39101999

PHI 140322

PHI 331829

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0028 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 38.0969

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5398

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49 n.246

Korhonen, K. 2007. Erudite forgeries or families seeking distinction? Cesare Gaetani's inscriptions from Syracuse. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.* 161: 291-298.

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